

Phy2Climate: Life Cycle Assessment of phytoremediation combined with biofuel production

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ABSTRACT

A significant area of land worldwide is contaminated and therefore unfit for any use. There is a huge need for bringing the polluted lands back to useable conditions in a harmless and sustainable way. In the Phy2Climate project, phytoremediation of contaminated sites in 4 regions all over the world is combined with innovative biomass processing technologies to produce clean biofuels for road and shipping transport as well as bio-coke as substitution of petroleum coke in the metallurgical industry. Greenhouse Gas reduction should be achieved by substituting fossil fuels and pet-coke as well as by enhancing the organic carbon content in the soil. To be able to judge the sustainability aspects of the technology, its environmental impact has to be analyzed in terms of the whole life cycle. This work presents the results of the first iteration of Life Cycle Assessment of phytoremediation and biofuel production. Primary inventory data have been collected from four pilot phytoremediation sites and from the biorefinery and supplemented with secondary data based on literature review and own mathematical calculations. The data have been then fed into a LCA model of pilot sites and biorefinery prepared in *LCA for Experts* software. Environmental impacts have been calculated using Environmental Footprint 3.1 methodology. The results confirm positive impact of phytoremediation on the ecotoxicity and human toxicity impact categories, as well as show the potential of Phy2Climate approach in the field of reduction of emissions of greenhouse gases.

1. Introduction

Land contamination is inevitably rooted in the progressing industrialization and has spread worldwide. It poses numerous problems: arable land depletion, hazardous leachates that can contaminate underground waters, and biodiversity loss, to name a few. Anthropogenic activities such as mining, oil and ore processing, pesticides and fertilizers overuse, and improper landfilling can contaminate nearby lands with organic and inorganic pollutants. One of the most persistent and hazardous is contamination with heavy metals that, when entering a food chain, accumulate in the soft tissues of animals and people, increasing risk of cancer, neurodegenerative diseases, internal organs damage, and autoimmune diseases [1]. Organic pollutants such as petroleum hydrocarbons are also a threat to the ecosystem, affecting soil microbiota, plants, and water resources [2,3].

Several non-biological approaches such as soil washing, stabilization, or chemical oxidation can be used for land decontamination. However, biological methods, including phytoremediation, are considered more ecological and more cost-effective, thus receiving an increasing scientific attention [1,4–8].

Phytoremediation relies on the ability of some plants to extract and store persistent contaminants in high amounts. These plants, called hyperaccumulators, can immobilize heavy metals in their tissue. Organic pollutants such as petroleum hydrocarbons can also be addressed by plant-assisted remediation. These toxins are not accumulated but instead are degraded by fungi and bacteria through the process called rhizodegradation, in which plants are providing habitat for the soil microorganisms [2,3].

The plants harvested after hydrocarbons phytoremediation are free of contamination, whereas the utilization of hyperaccumulators used for

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heavy metals removal poses yet another challenge. Several methods to dispose of contaminated biomass have been explored, e.g. composting, thermochemical conversion, and underground storage in mines [9–11]. The recovery of metals is also pursued to increase the ecological and economic benefits of the phytoremediation endeavor [9].

Compliant with the circular economy principles, thermochemical conversion of biomass harvested from heavy metal-contaminated lands can become a source of renewable energy and can help recover the metals. The thermochemical conversion reactor (gasifier or pyrolyzer) yields direct products such as bio-oil and syngas, while heavy metals concentrated in the residual bio-char can be recovered in pyrometallurgical processing plant. A standalone biomass conversion reactor can be extended into a full biorefinery plant in which refined transportation fuels can be produced by bio-oil refining and syngas-to-liquid conversion [12–14]. This idea was explored in the Phy2Climate project, and the life cycle assessment of the Phy2Climate project case study is the scope of this paper.

2. Description of the Phy2Climate project

The Phy2Climate project involves phytoremediation of four pilot sites (in Argentina, Lithuania, Serbia and Spain), which are contaminated with the most common soil contaminants worldwide – heavy metals and hydrocarbons. Because these sites are currently not used for agricultural activities, the phytoremediation pilots will produce energy crops with no indirect Land Use Change (iLUC) issues. The energy crops will be processed in a pilot biorefinery run by Fraunhofer Institute in Germany to produce several types of biofuels for the road and marine transport sectors, as well as bio-coke which can be a substitution of petroleum coke in the metallurgical industry. This approach has a potential to contribute to global reductions of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, mainly due to the avoided consumption of fossil fuels. The idea of the project is presented in Fig. 1.

For the phytoremediation process the soils were first characterized by physical and chemical analysis of collected samples. Sampling and analysis will be continued and periodically carried out during the phytoremediation process to monitor the progress in decontamination of the sites. Second, pot trials in controlled conditions were carried out in order to choose the optimal plant species and blend of soil amendments, fertilisers and biostimulants. In parallel, site preparation activities were carried out. This includes terrain delimitation, area division into control and experimental parcels, soil ploughing and levelling and (if required) installation of irrigation equipment. After seeding and planting, the main cultivation phase has begun, which (depending on the site) involves fertilizing and/or irrigating. During this phase, plant growth is

carefully monitored and a sampling programme is being performed in order to determine, among others, the bioaccumulation factor for the heavy metals and the rate of degradation of hydrocarbons. After harvesting, the energy crops have been analyzed in order to determine their final contaminant content. In case of lignocellulosic energy crops, the harvested biomass has been dried, chipped and pelletized. Depending on the energy crops and the site conditions, the crop cycle can be repeated up to three times during the project's duration. After the phytoremediation cycles are complete and the field research activities are fulfilled, the contaminated sites will be decommissioned.

The harvested energy crops from the phytoremediation sites have been shipped to the biorefinery in form of bulk biomass. The biomass will be fed to the Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR), which is a combination of intermediate pyrolysis with a post-reforming step. The TCR process produces bio-coke and three intermediate products: TCR-oil, TCR-gas and TCR-water. The TCR-oil distillation fractions are aimed to reach the ISO 8217 for distillate marine fuel (light fraction) and residual marine fuel (heavy fraction). The TCR-gas will feed Gas to Liquid (GtL) plant. The GtL will target the production of EN590 and EN228 gasoline as end products. In the initial concept of the biorefinery, the diesel and gasoline fractions will be produced via Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. Additional hydrogen is needed to ensure a high liquid yield and carbon use efficiency in the GtL process. To cover this need, TCR-water will be used as hydrogen source. The technology of Electro-oxidation will serve two simultaneous purposes: purification of the TCR-water by oxidation of the residual organic compounds and hydrogen provision for the GtL by water electrolysis. The scheme of the technological pathway within the biorefinery is presented in Fig. 2.

The Phy2Climate consortium unites 16 partners from 9 different countries with strong interdisciplinary expertise in the fields of project management, soil remediation & phytoremediation, advanced biofuel technologies, environmental and social sustainability, legal analysis, business development and communication & dissemination [15]. The project consists of several Work Packages. Findings from other Work Packages have already been published in numerous papers [16–21]. This article presents the work done within Work Package 4, which aims at evaluating the environmental impacts of the investigated technology. Because the technology affects several branches of the economy, analysing its impacts requires the use of a methodology capable of taking into account the environmental effects within a global balance boundary – Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

3. Life cycle assessment methodology

Life Cycle Assessment is a methodology commonly used to evaluate

Fig. 1. Overview of the Phy2Climate project [15].

Fig. 2. Technological scheme of the initial concept of the biorefinery.

the impacts of various processes or products on the natural environment, considering all stages of the life cycle: from obtaining the materials needed for production, through the manufacturing process, usage, to liquidation and waste management. It is also called a „cradle to grave” analysis. The procedure of LCA is standardized [22] and contains the following phases [23]:

- Definition of goal and scope of the analysis. The analyzed process or product must be precisely defined. Application of the study and the level of detail must be determined. Technological, geographical and temporal boundaries of the analyzed system must be delineated. A „functional unit”, to which the numerical results of the analysis will be referred must be defined. A set of impact assessment indicators appropriate to the study must be chosen.
- Life Cycle Inventory (LCI). All relevant flows of substances and energy crossing the boundary of the analyzed system, including wastes, must be identified and quantified. This stage requires compiling a diagram of flows between various sub-processes which constitute the analyzed process.
- Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA). The results of the Inventory stage must be assigned to relevant impact categories and subsequently characterized (recalculated into impact indicators). The results can also be normalized to facilitate a comparative analysis.
- Interpretation. Results from the Assessment phase shall be critically analyzed and interpreted. Limitations of the performed study should be discussed and conclusions should be drawn. A legible report from the study, tailored to the target audience, should be prepared.

3.1. Literature review on LCA approaches to soil remediation

Life Cycle Assessment has been applied for some phytoremediation projects globally and the results of these studies have been reported in the literature. However, the number of papers on this topic is still scarce, as highlighted in review articles [24–27].

Table 1 presents a summary of the literature review, with focus on the core elements of LCA, such as functional units and impact categories. The papers deal with removal of a variety of contaminants from the soil,

including heavy metals, hydrocarbons and overdosed fertilizers.

Majority of the reviewed LCA studies have a comparative character, with the goal of comparing the environmental impacts of phytoremediation with those of alternative remediation options, usually excavation-and-refill [28,30,32,33,37–39]. There are also examples of LCAs comparing various crops that can be used for phytoremediation ([38,31]) and non-comparative LCAs, such as [29] which focuses on resilience of phytoremediation to the rise of sea level. Some studies are restricted to evaluation of carbon footprint (global warming potential) of phytoremediation instead of full environmental assessment [30,34].

The usual system boundary adopted in the LCA studies is presented in Fig. 3. It contains the following processes: site preparation, plantation and cultivation of the plants, harvest and subsequent transportation of biomass either to a landfill or to an incineration facility, where electric energy is additionally produced. However, study [32] assumed that the harvested biomass will be left on the site. It is acceptable if the main contaminant are hydrocarbons, but such approach would not be possible for the case of sites contaminated with heavy metals. All of these cases represent the cradle-to-grave approach.

The primary function of phytoremediation, or any method of remediation for that matter, is the removal of contaminants from the soil. This is usually reflected in the functional unit of LCA, which is defined as “treatment of certain area (m^2)” [30,32,33,38,39,34,35] or “treatment of certain volume (m^3)” [29,41] of soil. However, the level of treatment rarely is quantitatively described in the definition of the functional unit, instead expressions such as “achieving clean soil” [32] or “land that can be safely used” [34] are used. Exceptions are [33,38,39,35], where the cleanliness of soil has been explicitly defined in terms of concentration of the contaminants. An example of a different definition of functional unit - production of 1 kg of dry biomass - can be found in Refs. [31,40]. In the case of [31] this can be explained by specificity of the case: the “contaminant” to be extracted by the plants is overdosed fertilizer.

Defining the temporal system boundary for phytoremediation is problematic due to long time needed to reduce the level of contamination in the soil, counted in years. Additionally, the required time may significantly differ for various contaminants which are to be removed [35]. This problem becomes especially apparent when phytoremediation is compared with excavation-and-refill, which can be

Table 1
Summary of literature review of Life Cycle Assessment of phytoremediation.

Ref.	Year	Country	Description	Goal and scope	Functional unit	Notable inventory entries	Impact categories
[28]	2021	Taiwan	Heavy metal extraction (Cr, Ni and Cu) from soil by two plant species	Comparison of environmental performances for phytoextraction and conventional remediation - excavation and refill at two contaminated sites	One-time operation of excavation-and-refill and one-year operation of phytoremediation	Biomass yield, fuel, fertilizers, metal concentration in plants	Endpoints (IMPACT method): human health, ecosystem quality, climate change, resources
[29]	2019	United States of America	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with tetrachloroethylene, vulnerable to a rise of sea level	Assessment of resilience of phytoremediation to climate change (rise of sea level)	Treatment of a 9000 m ³ volume of a tetrachloroethylene-contaminated aquifer	Irrigation material, fuel, biomass yield, carbon storage by plants	Endpoint (ReCiPe method): human health, ecosystems, resources Midpoint: vapor intrusion, surface water
[30]	2019	Italy	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with As and Pb	Assessment of global warming potential considering different destinations for the harvested biomass (disposal, combustion or pyrolysis), and a comparison with excavation and landfill disposal of contaminated soil	Treatment of 1 m ² of contaminated site	Biomass yield, fertilizer, mobilizing agents, water, transport	Global warming potential
[31]	2010	China	Phytoremediation of agricultural fields with nitrogen fertilizer overdose by three maize-based cropping systems	Evaluation of phytoremediation technology in an arable field and analysis of the impacts of cropping systems-based phytoremediation practices on the environment	Production of 1 ton of dry biomass	Fuel, pesticides, biomass yield, emission of harmful gases	Midpoint: depletion of abiotic resources, global warming, acidification, eutrophication, human toxicity, water eco-toxicity, terrestrial eco-toxicity
[32]	2011	Sweden	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with mineral oil	Comparison of phytoremediation with remediation by the means of excavation-and-refill; identification of processes with highest environmental impacts for optimization purposes	Remediation of a 5000 m ² site to achieve clean soil	Fertilizers, transport, agricultural activities	Endpoint (ReCiPe method): human health, ecosystem, resources Midpoint: global warming, ozone depletion, photochemical oxidation, acidification, eutrophication
[33]	2015	Spain	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with Pb	Sustainability assessment and comparison of phytoremediation with subsequent biofuel production, phytoremediation with biomass landfilling and remediation by the means of excavation-and-refill	Decontamination of 1 ha to achieve Pb concentration at the level 70 mg Pb/kg dry mass of soil	Fertilizers, transport, biomass yield, synthetic natural gas production	Midpoint (ReCiPe method): land occupation, land transformation, particulate matter formation, climate change, fossil depletion
[34]	2012	Belgium	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with Cd	Calculation of the potential of CO ₂ abatement by three phytoremediation crops	A hectare of land that can be safely used	Biomass yield, energy production from biomass, fuel, fertilizers	Global warming potential
[35]	2008	Holland	Remediation of a site contaminated with Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd	Development of an innovative decision support tool for sustainable land management	Cleaning 0.1625 ha of site to reach target values of contaminant concentrations	Seeds, transport, biomass yield	Impact on water, human health, climate change, resources
[36]	2008	–	Phytoremediation as an alternative method for landfill capping	Comparison of environmental impacts of phytoremediation-based landfill capping with the traditional technology	Treatment of leachate from a landfill (m ³ /year)	Seedlings, transport, water	Climate change, energy consumption, water use
[37]	2022	United States of America	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with Pb and using biomass as feedstock for the biorefinery system	Analysis of the environmental impacts of the production of biochemicals from switchgrass grown in lead contaminated soil and comparison to the production of the same products obtained from fossil fuels refinery system with lead removal by ex-situ extraction from equally sized plot of land	Processing 8.15 tons (on dry basis) of switchgrass	Fertilizers, transport, agricultural activities, energy input, biorefinery outputs	Greenhouse gas emissions, Cumulative energy demand, CML 2 Baseline (human health and ecosystem)
[38]	2024	Spain	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with Cu	Analysis of phytoextraction of copper with <i>B. juncea</i> and <i>M. sativa</i> and comparison with soil washing and soil excavation	Decontamination of 1 ha of the considered soil (20 cm depth) up to the maximum Cu concentration allowed by government regulations	Agricultural activities, fertilizers, energy inputs, biomass yield	CML 2001 (global warming potential category, acidification and eutrophication potentials, ecotoxicity and human toxicity potentials), EFP 3.1 (water use), direct and indirect primary energy use
[39]	2022	Spain	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with Pb	Assessing environmental performance of	Decontamination of 1 ha of the considered soil (20 cm	Agricultural activities,	CML 2001 (global warming potential category,

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Ref.	Year	Country	Description	Goal and scope	Functional unit	Notable inventory entries	Impact categories
				phytoremediation with <i>F. arundinacea</i> (with further landfilling or energy recovery) in comparison to soil washing and soil excavation	depth) up to the maximum Pb concentration allowed by government regulations	fertilizers, energy inputs, biomass yield	acidification and eutrophication potentials, ecotoxicity and human toxicity potentials), EFP 3.1 (water use), direct and indirect primary energy use
[40]	2022	Italy	Phytoremediation of a site contaminated with heavy metals	Assessing energy and environmental impacts of industrial hemp cultivation for phytoremediation of soil contaminated with heavy metals and using the biomass as an energy resource	1 kg of dry matter industrial hemp product and 1 ha of phytoremediated area	Fertilizers, water, fuel consumption, biomass yield	Cumulative energy demand (CED), climate change
[41]	2024	France	Phytoremediation of chloride-rich marine dredged sediment	Evaluation of feasibility and sustainability of phytoremediation of chloride-rich marine dredged sediment, using <i>Arundo Donax</i> along with biomass valorization	In-situ treatment of 1 m ³ of sediment	Agricultural activities, energy inputs, biomass yield, emissions	ReCiPe midpoint

Fig. 3. Typical system boundary in LCA of phytoremediation.

performed in several days. In Ref. [28] the problem propagated to functional unit, defined as “one-time operation of excavation-and-refill and one-year operation of phytoremediation”, which clearly does not serve a proper base for comparison from the perspective of the actual function of these activities. Despite the inadequate definition of functional unit, an additional comparison of the methods under an assumption of the same amount of removed heavy metals was presented.

The type of inventory data for phytoremediation is a direct consequence of the assumed system boundary (see Fig. 3). It includes, first of all, the consumption of resources during the site preparation and cultivation of plants phases: seeds, water, and fertilizers. If some mobilizing agents are used to enhance phytoextraction, they are inventoried as well. Operation of agricultural equipment is associated with consumption of fuel and other resources, such as lubricants. Furthermore, transport of biomass to the treatment facility (either landfill or incineration plant) is an important element of the inventory, as it is also associated with fuel consumption and emissions of harmful gases from the vehicles. The distance to the treatment facility is an important factor. On the “output” side, the main element of the inventory is the yield of biomass. However, it does not need to be inventoried if it is not collected, as in the case of [32]. If the biomass is used for energy production, then the flows associated with this process have to be inventoried. Surprisingly, not all studies clearly report the uptake of contaminants by the plants (phytoextraction rates). Only one of the reviewed studies treats the contaminants extracted from the soil as a material flow crossing the system boundary and interprets it as “negative” emissions to the soil [33].

It is a common practice to use some kind of well recognized life cycle impact models, such as ReCiPe [32,33,29], which aggregates the environmental impacts to several endpoint categories: human health, ecosystems and resources. Standard midpoint categories, such as acidification, eutrophication, human toxicity and eco-toxicity are also widely used. Due to the potential of biomass to replace fossil fuels, the category “global warming potential” has a special significance and

sometimes is the only investigated impact category [30,34]. Categories of land occupation and land transformation also seem to be important due to their direct connection with the function of the investigated process [32,33].

The reviewed comparative LCAs all conclude that the environmental impacts of phytoremediation are lower than the impacts of excavation-and-refill site remediation. Sometimes the impacts are even negative, especially in the categories “resources depletion” (thanks to substitution of fossil fuels in the biomass combustion scenario [33,35]) and “global warming potential” (for the same reason, or, if the biomass is not incinerated, due to carbon dioxide sequestration by plants [30]).

A disadvantage of phytoremediation (especially in the case of heavy-metal contaminated soil) often highlighted in the studies is the problem of disposal of biomass. The impacts of end-of-life management of biomass are often overlooked [26]. Landfilling is the least desirable option; instead the biomass should be composted or converted thermochemically (combustion, gasification, pyrolysis, torrefaction). Heavy metals can be recovered from ashes or leachate [24].

The contribution of various phases of the life cycle to the impacts is case-specific. For example [32] finds the impacts caused by transport to be the highest, while [33] found them negligible. As mentioned before, even though phytoremediation is characterized by much lower environmental impacts than “conventional” site remediation, it is considered inefficient from the time perspective and the excavation-and-refill method may still be the preferred one if the duration of the cleaning activities is a decisive factor [35].

Particularly interesting from the perspective of Phy2Climate project is the research published in Refs. [33,37]. In Ref. [33] biomass harvested from the remediated site was used to produce synthetic natural gas through a multistage process. The impact of consumption of an equivalent amount of natural gas was subtracted from the environmental impact of phytoremediation + biofuel production process. The results show that not only this option is much more sustainable than biomass landfilling, excavation-and-refill or “no action” scenarios, but it also is

characterized by a negative single score, interpreted as an overall environmental benefit. In Ref. [37] the biomass was processed in a biorefinery (including hydrolysis and pyrolysis steps) to produce ethanol, biodiesel, phenols and biochar. Environmental impacts were compared to a reference system consisting of ex-situ soil remediation and fossil fuel refinery. Results showed that the phytoremediation approach has significantly lower environmental impacts in all assessed categories except for acidification and eutrophication.

3.2. Literature review on LCA approaches to biorefineries

Biofuels are meant to replace fossil fuels, so their use is expected to have a positive environmental effect in terms of climate change. On the other hand, growing bioenergy crops (which is one of two ways of obtaining biomass, the other one being residues from agriculture, forestry or wood industry) requires land and is associated with intensive use of fertilizers, therefore it causes environmental burdens in areas such as eutrophication, acidification and land use. Performing a LCA of biofuel production process is helpful to understand the trade-offs between these impacts [42].

Biorefining can be defined as a “sustainable processing of biomass into a spectrum of marketable products and energy”. Therefore, the biorefinery concept is analogous to today’s petroleum refinery, which produces multiple fuels and products from petroleum. Biorefinery systems are characterized by multiple high value products, so particular attention is required in the choice of the functional unit in LCA and the potential allocation criteria [42].

There is a broad library of publications devoted to LCA of biomass conversion systems [43,44]. In Table 2 only a selection of those explicitly referring to “biorefineries” processing vegetal biomass is included.

Examples of goals of LCA of biorefinery processes include [59]:

- Identifying consequences of using land in various ways, thus finding the optimal use of land,
- Finding the optimal conversion pathway for biomass or waste,
- Assessing the environmental impact of a selected biorefinery product and its use,
- Examining the choice of combination of output products on the environmental impact,
- Assessing the environmental impacts of a biorefinery itself and identifying the hotspots of a biorefinery process

The first two bullet points in the list above focus on the use of feedstock and the associated functional unit in this case would be a unit of mass of input biomass or a unit of area of land. The next two points are product-oriented. The functional unit in such case refers either to the unit of energy of the final products or to the function fulfilled by consumption of this product (for example person-km for fuels used in transport; to account for different engine efficiencies) [59]. It could also be linked to mass of volume of products, but this is not recommended because the bioproducts may differ in composition and properties from the replaced conventional products [43]. Furthermore, great care must be taken when defining the functional unit, because the choice of the main product is an arbitrary decision and the subsequent selection of allocation criteria can substantially influence the results. To work around this problem, a combination of products can be defined as a functional unit. Nevertheless, it is recommended to express the results per unit of agricultural land, since the available area for the production of biomass raw materials is the biggest limitation for the production of biofuels [42]. The last bullet point is process-oriented and the functional unit could be defined as “construction of a biorefinery” [59].

Fig. 4 presents the typical system boundary for biorefinery LCAs for the “cradle-to-grave” approach. However, the most common approach found in the literature is “cradle-to-gate” (omitting the use of biorefinery products). Approaches omitting the feedstock production (“gate-to-

gate” or “gate-to-grave”) can also be found in the literature [43,44]. As the system boundaries of phytoremediation and biorefinery processes partially overlap, the inventory of biorefinery LCA will include similar items as for site remediation LCA: biomass yield, use of fertilizers, herbicides, fuel for agricultural equipment and transport. In addition, mass and energy flows within the biorefinery need to be inventoried, especially the final products.

As mentioned above, handling multifunctionality of biorefineries is a challenging task. The method of allocation is often unsuitable, because it can be difficult to find a common appropriate allocation criterion. Mass-based allocation neglects the composition of products, and energy-based allocation can also be unjustified, since not all products have an energy purpose [43,59]. Additionally, the final use of various biofuel products and by-products greatly influences the results of the analysis, therefore allocation should be avoided and appropriate system expansion used instead. The energy and GHG balances of bioenergy systems (including biorefineries) should always be compared with fossil reference systems [42]. In practice system expansion method is used most frequently [44].

Global warming potential, already being the most prominent impact category investigated in LCAs, is even more relevant in the case of biomass conversion systems. Aside from the substitution of fossil fuels and related emissions (“fossil carbon”), there is another contributor to the greenhouse gases balance, namely “biogenic carbon”, associated with absorption and emission of carbon by plants and soils, as well as land use change effects. It is recommended to inventory biogenic carbon separately from fossil carbon [59]. The time lag between uptake and release of CO₂ by biomass, significant for biorefinery products that are not meant to be used as fuels (combusted), is usually not included in LCA of biorefineries, although it should at least be discussed in the study [59].

When LCA of biorefinery systems is not limited to evaluation of global warming potential, usually some widespread life cycle impact models (e.g. ReCiPe, CML, IMPACT) are used and the results are aggregated into midpoint [45,47,50,51] or endpoint [48,49,52] categories.

In general, the LCA studies of biorefineries conclude that they are environmentally more favorable than reference fossil systems, especially in the climate change and resources categories [45,49,46]. On the other hand, biomass-based systems may be less environmentally friendly in the category ecosystem quality due to impacts generated in the cultivation of biomass phase [45,49]. The source of biomass plays the most important role [42].

From the perspective of Phy2Climate project, LCA studies focusing on the thermocatalytic reforming process (TCR) and production of biofuels and biocoke are particularly interesting. Carbon footprint analysis of TCR has been performed in Ref. [60]. Two different feedstocks have been compared: residues from olive wood pruning and digestate from anaerobic digestion. For the olive wood case, the system boundary does not include the cultivation phase, although the absorption of CO₂ by the plants is taken into account. Various scenarios of utilization of the products of TCR have been analyzed: either off-site energy production (or soil amendment in the case of biochar) or on-site consumption to cover energy needs of the process. It was found that the scenarios in which biochar is used as soil amendment result in the lowest carbon footprint. If the carbon absorption by plants is considered, the footprint becomes negative. From the comparison of results for both analyzed feedstocks, it is evident that the overall performance of the TCR is strongly related to the characteristics of the biomass to be converted, because it influences both the pre-treatment requirements as well as the quality of the obtained products.

4. Definition of goal and scope

LCA of the Phy2Climate project is planned for Research & Development purposes. The goal of LCA is to evaluate the sustainability of phytoremediation of contaminated lands with subsequent production of

Table 2
Summary of literature review of Life Cycle Assessment of biorefineries.

Ref.	Year	Description	Goal and scope	Functional unit	Handling of multifunctionality	Impact categories
[45]	2009	Biorefinery which produces bioethanol, bioenergy, and biochemical from switchgrass	Comparing biorefinery with reference fossil systems	Treatment of 477 Gg of dry biomass per year	Not applicable	CML method: Global warming potential, abiotic depletion, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, water ecotoxicity, eutrophication, acidification, Global warming potential
[46]	2019	Biorefinery producing amino acids from grass silage	Analysis of ecological aspects of various processing concepts for combining a biorefinery and biogas plant	Production of 1 kg of amino acid	Allocation based on mass	ReCiPe method: Global warming potential, fossil depletion, human toxicity, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity
[47]	2020	Biorefinery producing furfural and lactic acid from vine shoots	Assessment of the environmental impact of using vine shoots as feedstock to produce chemicals and comparison with reference systems	Production of 1 kg of lactic acid	Allocation based on economic value	ReCiPe method: Global warming potential, fossil depletion, human toxicity, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity
[48]	2017	Biorefinery producing biodiesel from castor	Investigating the environmental consequences of castor biodiesel production and consumption ("well to wheel") and comparison with fossil reference system	Obtaining 1 GJ of energy via combustion of biodiesel	System expansion with substitution (credit)	IMPACT method: human health, ecosystem quality, climate change, resources
[49]	2011	Biorefinery producing bioethanol from wood residues	Comparison of environmental impacts of a biorefinery based on wood residues with a biorefinery based on corn feedstock and with a conventional refinery	Production of 1 kg of fuel and 1 kWh of electricity	Allocation based on economic value	Eco-indicator method: human health, ecosystem quality, resources
[50]	2019	Biorefinery producing isobutene and xylo-oligosaccharides from corn stover or wheat straw	Comparison of environmental impacts of biorefineries in two different geographical locations and identification of the main factors affecting sustainability	1 Mg of lignocellulosic feedstock	Allocation based on economic value	ReCiPe method: climate change, ozone depletion, marine eutrophication, particulate matter formation, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, agricultural land occupation, water depletion, fossil depletion
[51]	2016	Biorefineries producing various products from beech wood	Comparison of environmental impacts of four conceptual beech wood based biorefineries	Not reported (biorefinery as a whole?)	System expansion with substitution (credit)	ReCiPe method: Freshwater eutrophication, particulate formation, ecotoxicity, human toxicity, radiation, climate change, agricultural land occupation, natural land transformation, ozone depletion, photochemical ozone formation, terrestrial acidification, urbanland occupation, fossil fuel consumption, minerals consumption
[52]	2015	Biorefinery integrated with pulp and paper mill using hot water extraction technology	Comparison of environmental impacts of five biorefinery production pathways	Portfolio of products that was generated by different biorefinery options using 310 Gg per year of dilute hemicellulose stream	System expansion with substitution (credit)	IMPACT method: climate change, human health, ecosystem quality, resources
[37]	2022	Biorefinery processing switchgrass from a site contaminated with Pb	Analysis of the environmental impacts of the production of biochemicals from switchgrass grown in lead contaminated soil and comparison to the production of the same products obtained from fossil fuels refinery system with lead removal by ex-situ extraction from equally sized plot of land	Processing 8.15 tons (on dry basis) of switchgrass	None - Comparison with equivalent alternative (fossil fuel based) system	CML 2 Baseline method: greenhouse gas emissions, cumulative energy demand, human health, ecosystem
[53]	2023	Biorefinery producing biofuel from lignocellulosic biomass	Assessing environmental impacts of producing advanced biofuels from lignin-rich stream or corn stover feedstocks through a combined hydrothermal liquefaction - aqueous phase reforming plant.	Producing 1 MJ of biofuel	Not applicable	CML 2001 baseline method: global warming potential, acidification potential, eutrophication potential, fossil depletion potential
[54]	2023	Biorefinery producing hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF)	Comparing the environmental performance of biobased HMF production from two sources (maize or miscanthus)	Producing 1 kg of HMF	Allocation by mass/ Economic allocation	ReCiPe method: global warming potential, terrestrial acidification, particulate matter formation, land occupation,

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Ref.	Year	Description	Goal and scope	Functional unit	Handling of multifunctionality	Impact categories
[55]	2023	Biorefinery converting forest residues to bio-crude oil	Quantifying the environmental performance of pyrolysis biorefineries fed with primary forest residues in comparison to leaving the forest residues to decay	Management of 1000 kg of dry biomass	System expansion with substitution (credit)	ecosystem quality, human health, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication Environmental Footprint method: climate change, human toxicity, resource use, eutrophication, acidification, ozone depletion
[56]	2021	Production of ethanol and electricity under a biorefinery concept using coffee cut-stems as feedstock	Determining environmental impacts and hotspots associated with production of coffee cut-stems and generation of energy under a biorefinery concept	Generation of 1 MJ of energy (in the form of ethanol or electricity)	System expansion with substitution (credit)	ReCiPe method: climate change, ozone depletion, acidification, eutrophication, human toxicity, ecotoxicity, fossil depletion, water depletion, agricultural land occupation
[57]	2018	Production of biodiesel, electricity, ethanol, heat, glycerol, and/or biomethane from <i>Eruca sativa</i>	Comparison of three different biorefinery scenarios (feedstock processing alternatives)	1 GJ of biodiesel	System expansion with substitution (credit)	IMPACT 2002 + method: Greenhouse gas balance, resources damage category, human health damage category, ecosystem quality damage category, energy indices, water footprint GHG emissions
[58]	2015	Production of ethanol from corn stover	Evaluating impacts of process technology development and regional aspects on life cycle GHG emissions associated with ethanol produced from corn stover in the United States	1 MJ of ethanol	System expansion and mass allocation	

Fig. 4. Typical generalized system boundary in LCA of biorefinery system (top) and reference fossil system (bottom).

biofuels and bio-coke from the harvested biomass. Since the investigated technology is characterized by low readiness level (TRL 3), it is important to identify the environmental impacts before taking it to a higher level (TRL 5) and commissioning a large-scale commercial plant. Results of the LCA can possibly help in optimization of some aspects of the technology, e.g. selection of plant species for phytoremediation. In the long term, the LCA could be treated as a decision support tool for policymakers and companies commercializing the technology.

As explained before, the investigated technology consists of two subsystems which can operate independently: phytoremediation, whose main function is the restoration of land to arable quality, and biorefinery, whose function is converting biomass into biofuels. These subsystems will be first assessed separately (using different functional units), and afterwards an assessment of the combined process will be carried out.

The main function of the phytoremediation technology is “restoration of contaminated land to arable quality in under 20 years”. With regard to this function, the functional unit is therefore chosen to be “phytoremediation of 1 ha of contaminated land for 1 year”.

Such definition of the functional unit does not fully reflect the function of the technology (in terms of soil quality), but adopting a seemingly more suitable definition - “phytoremediation of 1 ha of contaminated land to achieve arable quality” would cause problems with data acquisition. Furthermore, it could cause problems with interpretation of the results and combining this process with the biorefinery. The amount of time needed to achieve the desired effect will be different for different sites and different crops. Since the overall environmental impacts of Phy2Climate technology will depend on the

utilization of harvested biomass due to environmental credits from production of biofuel, this may lead to phytoremediation processes which take longer time achieving more favorable (lower) environmental impacts, because more biofuels will be produced from the remediated land. This is not in line with the main function of the project, which is to restore the land as soon as possible.

The functional unit of biorefinery has been adopted as “**processing 3900 Mg of dry biomass**”. This particular number is related to the planned capacity of the biorefinery and corresponds to one year operation of the plant. Such definition of functional unit matches the assumptions in the business model of Phy2Climate, which is being developed in parallel.

The functional unit for the generalized combined process is equivalent to the functional unit of the biorefinery, but can be expressed as “**processing 3900 Mg of dry biomass harvested from contaminated sites undergoing phytoremediation for one year**”. The two subprocesses are connected with each other via the reference flow “**1 kg of biomass harvested from the site and processed at the biorefinery**”. This reference flow is related to the area of remediated land through the biomass yield (expressed in kg per ha per year).

Multifunctionality of the investigated technology, namely the production of biofuels and bio-coke, will be handled via the method of substitution (system expansion and credit). The substituted products are market-average fossil-derived fuels: coke, diesel, marine fuel and gasoline. The inventory of the substituted reference process will be subtracted from the inventory of the investigated technology. The reference flows of the biorefinery products – biofuels and bio-coke – will be expressed per unit of higher calorific value, as “**1 MJ of biofuel or bio-**

coke”.

The main processes included within the technological system boundary are depicted in Fig. 5. Background processes of the technosphere are not depicted; instead the blue arrows represent connections with these background processes such as supply of fuels and electric energy or production of fertilizers. Manufacturing of machines needed during the phytoremediation activities is excluded from the system boundary. Decommissioning of biorefinery is also not considered in the analysis – it is assumed that after the phytoremediation action is completed, the biorefinery will still process biomass from different sources. The final use of produced fuels is only considered in terms of their combustion, in order to differentiate between biogenic and non-biogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, the copper smelting process is excluded from the system boundary. This is justified by the fact that virtually the only difference between this process within the Phy2Climate project and the substituted process is the type of used coke and therefore excluding the copper smelting process would not change the outcome of the assessment. The metal and metalloid contaminants extracted from the soil are expected to translocate to bio-coke and eventually become admixtures of the produced copper. Under such scenario, these contaminants will not be re-released to the ecosphere. Note that the process of plants cultivation may be interpreted as associated with negative emissions to the soil.

Construction phase of the biorefinery is not included in the inventory, in order to adhere to the provisions of greenhouse gas emissions included in the Renewable Energy Directive [61], which states that “emissions from the manufacture of machinery and equipment shall not be taken into account”. It is a common approach in LCA of energy conversion systems - especially those that involve combustion of fuels - to neglect the construction phase, because its impacts are low compared to the impacts of operation phase.

The investigated technology has a potentially broad impact on all three “areas of protection”, therefore a decision has been made not to exclude any of the standard impact categories. They are listed in Table 3, although only selected, most relevant results are presented in this paper. The analysis has been carried out using *LCA for Experts* software (by Sphera) with the use of Environmental Footprint 3.1 methodology (recommended by the European Commission [62]). Environmental impacts have been assessed on the midpoint level. Weighting of results is not planned.

5. Life cycle inventory

For easier readability and interpretation of the LCIA results, the inventory elements of phytoremediation have been aggregated into five groups, and of biomass processing into 10 groups. The groups with the assigned colours are presented in Fig. 6. The same colours will be also used for presentation of results.

5.1. Phytoremediation

Life cycle inventory data for phytoremediation (e.g., amounts of energy and fuels, fertilizers, soil amendments, pesticides and water) has been collected by pilot site leaders. Table 4 contains a summary of the general information on the pilot sites: types of contaminants, cultivated plants and area.

Table 5 presents the summary of inventory; the listed values refer to 1 year of phytoremediation activity. The corresponding database items used in the modelling are also listed in the Table. They are of two types: (E) – elementary flows with assigned characterization factors (associated with emissions of substances to the ecosphere), and (P) – pre-defined processes included in the Sphera database (associated with production of goods).

The use of fuels has not been inventoried separately for each agricultural activity (e.g., soil preparation, fertilizing, harvest, transport). The presented numbers reflect aggregate fuel usage. Combustion of fuels has been modelled using the following processes: “GLO: Universal Tractor” for diesel and “GLO: Car, petrol, Euro 4” for gasoline.

Land occupation by the phytoremediation site is not included in the inventory. This is because in the case of phytoremediation, the polluted land is not a “resource” that is used to fulfil the function of the system; it is rather a part of the system itself.

Even though phytoremediation for one year (assumed in the functional unit) is most likely not enough to achieve arable quality of the land, land transformation has been included in the life cycle inventory. Inventory elements used in the model are listed in Table 6. Area of land undergoing transformation has been listed in Table 4. Impacts associated with land transformation are assigned to the “Land transformation” group (per Fig. 6).

Biomass production from the pilot sites after the first year is listed in Table 7.

Fig. 5. Technological system boundary for Life Cycle Assessment.

Table 3
List of impact categories investigated within the Environmental Footprint methodology.

Area of protection	Natural environment	Human health	Natural resources
Impact categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change (fossil, biogenic and land use change) Ozone depletion Ecotoxicity of freshwater (organics and inorganics) Acidification Eutrophication, marine Eutrophication, freshwater Eutrophication, terrestrial 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human toxicity, cancer (organics and inorganics) Human toxicity, non-cancer (organics and inorganics) Particulate matter Ionising radiation Photochemical ozone formation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land use Water use Resource use, fossils Resource use, minerals and metals

Fig. 6. Groups of activities related to environmental impacts of phytoremediation (left) and biomass processing (right).

Table 4
Main information on the pilot sites.

Site	Argentina (ARG)	Serbia (SRB)	Lithuania (LTU)	Spain (ESP)
Contaminants	Metals and metalloids	Heavy metals	Hydrocarbons	Hydrocarbons
Cultivated species	Native shrubs (plectrocarpa tetracantha, bulnesia retama, larrea cuneifolia, prosopis flexuosa), quinoa	Rapeseed	Herbaceous plants (tall fescue, perennial ryegrass, alfalfa, festuca perennis, bird's-foot trefoil), amaranthus, Jerusalem artichoke	Sorghum, rapeseed
Cultivated area	0.1 ha	0.24 ha	0.25 ha	0.80 ha

A very important element of the life cycle inventory of phytoremediation is the information on the amount of removed (or degraded) soil contaminants. It is included in the “land transformation” group (see Fig. 6). An absolute value (in kg) is required for the analysis. However, this quantity cannot be directly measured and instead has to be estimated. There are two possible approaches: one basing on the measurements of contaminant concentrations in the biomass – Equation (1), and another basing on the measurements of contaminant concentrations in the soil – Equation (2).

$$m_c = c_b \cdot m_b \tag{1}$$

$$m_c = \Delta c_s \cdot A_s \cdot d_s \cdot \rho_s \tag{2}$$

m_c – mass of removed contaminant, kg,

c_b – concentration of contaminant in biomass, kg/kg,
 Δc_s – change of concentration of contaminant in soil, kg/kg,
 d_s – depth of remediated soil, m,
 ρ_s – density of remediated soil, kg/m³.

This problem is not well documented in the literature and there is not a standard methodology of handling the decontamination of soil in LCA. It is not even common to include the (negative) emissions to soil in the inventory; often the aspect of decontamination is only addressed in the functional unit [63] (examples can be found in Refs. [30,32]). Studies [28,34] also do not include the negative emissions in the inventory, but estimate the amount of heavy metals removed from the soil using approach (1). Nevertheless, studies that include these emissions in the inventory can also be found [33,38,39].

Approach (1) is generally burdened with much lower uncertainty than approach (2). The main source of uncertainty is usually a very heterogenous spatial distribution of contaminants in the soil, which would require a very dense mesh of sampling points [64].

For the purpose of this study, the mass of heavy metals removed from the soil is estimated using approach (1), that is by multiplying the amount of harvested biomass by the average concentration of a given contaminant in the biomass. Unfortunately, this method cannot be applied in the case of hydrocarbons, which are degraded rather than extracted. For hydrocarbons, approach (2) is used, that is multiplying the change of their concentration in the soil by the mass of soil that undergoes phytoremediation. Such approach results in a rough estimate not only because of the abovementioned uncertainties of concentrations in soil, but also because the mass of soil is calculated by multiplying its volume by density. The density of soil has been measured on the pilot sites, but it is burdened by additional uncertainty. Depth of remediated soil has been assumed as 1 m. Results of calculations of the amount of removed contaminants are presented in Table 8. The corresponding database items used in the modelling are also listed in the Table.

Formula (2) is also the only possibility to estimate the “emissions” of

Table 5
Inventory of resources used during phytoremediation.

Flow	Unit	Pilot site				Database item
		ARG	SRB	LTU	ESP	
Gasoline	kg	14.7	-	-	-	(P) RER: Gasoline mix (regular) at filling station
Diesel	kg	275	16.8	589.5	173	(P) RER: Diesel mix at filling station
Electric energy	kWh	-	-	150	-	(P) RER: Electricity grid mix
Freshwater	dm ³	190190	-	-	216240	(E) Fresh water [Water]
Rainwater	dm ³	-	45	9000	-	(E) Rain water [Water]
Compost ^A	kg	3360	-	1800	21.6	None ^D
Dolomite ^B	kg	95424	-	-	-	(E) Dolomite [Non renewable resources]
NPK fertilizer	kg	-	-	105	4	(P) DE: NPK 15-15-15
Urea	kg	6	-	-	-	(P) DE: Urea (agrarian)
Ammonium sulphate	kg	-	30	6	-	(P) DE: Ammonium sulphate (Caprolactam production)
Potassium chloride	kg	-	-	8	-	(P) RER: Potassium chloride (KCl/MOP, 60% K ₂ O)
Cypermethrin	kg	-	0.008	-	-	(P) GLO: Pesticide (average) (E) Cypermethrin [Pesticides to agricultural soil]
Dicamba	kg	-	0.024	-	-	(P) GLO: Pesticide (average) (E) Dicamba [Pesticides to agricultural soil]
Dimoxystrobin	kg	-	0.008	-	-	(P) GLO: Pesticide (average) (E) Dimoxystrobin [Pesticides to agricultural soil]
Boscalid	kg	-	0.008	-	-	(P) GLO: Pesticide (average)
Biochar ^C	kg	-	-	-	10.8	None ^E

^A For ARG and ESP, data was provided in m³. Density of 400 kg/m³ was assumed.
^B Data was provided in m³. Density of 2840 kg/m³ was assumed.
^C Data was provided in m³. Density of 200 kg/m³ was assumed.
^D Production of compost has been excluded from the model.
^E Biochar is also one of the products of the analyzed technology. A loop-back approach will be used.

^A For ARG and ESP, data was provided in m³. Density of 400 kg/m³ was assumed.

^B Data was provided in m³. Density of 2840 kg/m³ was assumed.

^C Data was provided in m³. Density of 200 kg/m³ was assumed.

^D Production of compost has been excluded from the model.

^E Biochar is also one of the products of the analyzed technology. A loop-back approach will be used.

Table 6
Land transformation inventory elements used in the LCA model.

Pilot site	Database items used for land transformation	
ARG	From bare area (regionalized, AR)	To arable (regionalized, AR)
SRB	From field margins/hedgerows (regionalized, RS)	To arable (regionalized, RS)
LTU	From industrial area (regionalized, LT)	To arable (regionalized, LT)
ESP	From industrial area (regionalized, ES)	To arable (regionalized, ES)

macronutrients (nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium) as well as carbon into the soil. Results of calculations are presented in Table 9. Positive values represent an increase of content of a given element in the soil and negative values – a decrease. Since the presented results are very uncertain and unreliable (for example implying a change of 33 tons of Mg in the Lithuanian site), and for some sites no measurements have been carried out, the changes of macronutrients content in the soil are excluded from the life cycle inventory. This is also justified by the fact that the main focus of this LCA is the climate change impact

Table 7
Dry biomass output from the pilot sites.

Pilot site	ARG	SRB	LTU	ESP
Dry biomass output, kg	73 ^a	2500 ^b	370 ^c	1118 ^d
Biomass yield, kg/ha	727	10417	1480	1398

^a Including: 56 kg of quinoa (harvested after the 1st year) and an estimate of 50 kg of native shrubs (to be harvested after the 3rd year).

^b Estimate based on the number of plants and average dry mass of one plant at harvest.

^c Including: 160 kg of herbaceous plants, 167 kg of Jerusalem artichoke and 43 kg of amaranth.

^d Including: 1057 kg of sorghum and 61 kg of rape.

category, which is not affected by these “emissions”.

The model should account for the changes of carbon content in the soil. However the results of measurements and calculations (presented in Table 9) are also very uncertain and unreliable and for this reason it was decided not to consider them in the LCA. There is one more potential component of the carbon balance: carbon content in the biomass residues that are left on the site after harvest. It has not been quantified for the first iteration, but an attempt to estimate it will be included in the

Table 8
Inventory of contaminants removed from the soil (values in kg).

Contaminant	ARG ¹	SRB ²	LTU ³	ESP ⁴	Database item
Arsenic	0.034180 ±0.007747	-	-	-	(E) Arsenic [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Cadmium	0.050576 ±0.036498	0.001900	-	-	(E) Cadmium [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Chromium	-	0.003675	-	-	(E) Chromium [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Copper	0.052904 ±0.022830	0.013025	-	-	(E) Copper [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Lead	-	0.002100	-	-	(E) Lead [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Nickel	-	0.002700	-	-	(E) Nickel [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Zinc	0.334632 ±0.294354	0.077625	-	-	(E) Zinc [Heavy metals to agricultural soil]
Total petroleum hydrocarbons	-	706 ±42	3049 ±48	425	(E) Hydrocarbons, unspecified [Other emissions to agricultural soil]
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	-	2.85 ±0.17	-	3.60	(E) Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (unspecified) [Organic emissions to agricultural soil]
Polychlorinated biphenyls	-	0.21 ±0.01	-	-	(E) Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB unspecified) [Organic emissions to agricultural soil]
¹ Uncertainties of heavy metal concentrations in the biomass have been taken into account ² Only the uncertainty of soil density was taken into account; uncertainties of contaminant concentrations have not been reported ³ Only the uncertainty of soil density was taken into account; uncertainties of contaminant concentrations have not been reported ⁴ Neither uncertainties of soil density nor contaminant concentrations have been reported					

¹ Uncertainties of heavy metal concentrations in the biomass have been taken into account.

² Only the uncertainty of soil density was taken into account; uncertainties of contaminant concentrations have not been reported.

³ Only the uncertainty of soil density was taken into account; uncertainties of contaminant concentrations have not been reported.

⁴ Neither uncertainties of soil density nor contaminant concentrations have been reported.

Table 9
Inventory of the changes of soil macronutrients and carbon (values in kg).

Element	ARG ^a	SRB ^b	LTU ^c	ESP ^d
Nitrogen	Not measured	350 ± 390	3749 ± 56	-0.01
Potassium	Not measured	-2986 ± 1926	-5378 ± 81	-2240 ± 117
Phosphorus	Not measured	-809 ± 729	-1196 ± 18	102 ± 3
Magnesium	8934 ± 2933	-23785 ± 2075	-33055 ± 498	8750 ± 659
Calcium	30578 ± 6744	-5449 ± 917	Not measured	36840 ± 2659
Carbon	Not measured	10978 ± 38978	36554 ± 550	-1.5 ± 0.3

^a Both uncertainties of soil density and element concentrations in the soil have been taken into account.

^b Both uncertainties of soil density and element concentrations in the soil have been taken into account.

^c Only the uncertainty of soil density has been taken into account; uncertainties of element concentrations in the soil have not been reported.

^d Only the uncertainties of element concentrations in the soil have been taken into account; uncertainty of soil density has not been reported.

second iteration of the LCA.

5.2. Biorefinery

For the purpose of LCA the biorefinery could be treated as a “black box” process without distinguishing in detail between the various

components of the biorefinery. However, the biorefinery has been split into particular processes to allow for a more detailed sensitivity analysis. Biorefinery products and the avoided use of replaced fossil fuels have been also split into three groups (see Fig. 6).

Inventory data on the mass balance of the biorefinery is mostly basing on previously conducted experiments on TCR reactor and theoretical calculations performed by Fraunhofer Institute. For the energy balance of the biorefinery, a literature review supported by own mathematical models has been used to procure secondary data. Tables in this section list the sources of data: **F** for Fraunhofer or **L** for own literature review. General process design, as presented in Fig. 2, was used to identify energy and product streams for the LCI. For the first iteration of LCA, a basic scenario without internal heat and mass streams recirculation was considered, as the first approach to the biorefinery concept.

Average European grid electricity and average European thermal energy from natural gas have been assumed as sources of energy for the biorefinery. The idea is to use the average, easily available energy sources power the biorefinery. Using purely renewable energy sources (for example photovoltaics) to power the biorefinery would mean extending the system boundary of the LCA to additionally include construction of these new energy sources. This is out of the scope of the project and would obfuscate the analysis.

Biomass pretreatment involved drying, grinding, and pelletisation. Pelletized biomass is shipped to the biorefinery, where it undergoes thermochemical conversion into bio-coke, bio-oil, syngas, and pyrolysis water in the TCR reactor. Typically, the process is carried out under atmospheric pressure and inert atmosphere, with the reformer operating at around 700°C. Bio-coke produced in the TCR is destined for the copper smelter industry, not included in the biorefinery boundaries.

Liquid and gaseous products are directed to the purification and conversion units. Pyrolysis water is a waste stream that is purified in the electrooxidation unit before exiting the biorefinery. Liquid products are produced in two ways. The first one is the distillation of bio-oil. The second liquid fuel production method is gas-to-liquid (GtL) conversion preceded by gas cooling, cleaning, and compression (all these processes are included in the “Biorefinery: GtL” group according to Fig. 6). Hot syngas exits TCR reformer, and it was assumed that it is cooled down prior to the purification unit. Gas purification unit is aimed at moisture, sulfur and nitrogen removal in the acidic and basic scrubbers, fixed bed reactors and a cooling trap. Purified syngas together with hydrogen generated in the electrooxidation unit is directed to a gas compressor. The base case scenario, following mass balance provided by Fraunhofer, assumes utilization of CO as well as CO₂ in the GtL unit. The exact method, e.g., reversed water gas shift reaction, or direct Fischer–Tropsch conversion of CO₂, is not yet decided. A low-temperature Fischer–Tropsch reactor was assumed for the GtL unit. Liquid products (gasoline, kerosene and paraffin) are distilled in a separation column.

A distance of 100 km and transport by trucks (a process (P) “GLO: Truck-trailer, Euro 6 D-E, 34 - 40t gross weight/27t payload capacity”) are assumed for the transport of biomass. The fuel consumed during transport is assumed to be (P) “RER: Diesel mix at refinery”.

Table 10 presents the typical mass balance of the biorefinery for an input of 100 kg of dried biomass (10% moisture content). The intermediate flows exchanged between the components of the biorefinery are irrelevant from the perspective of LCA, but they are useful for estimation of the energy balance of particular components of the refinery. The

database items used for modelling are also listed in Table 10. For the produced biofuels, it is assumed that they will replace an equivalent amount of fossil fuels (in practice this is modelled by assuming negative flows of the replaced fossil fuels in the processes listed in Table 10). The use of biofuels is modelled by assuming positive emission of biogenic CO₂ from their combustion and equivalent negative emission of non-biogenic CO₂. Intermediate and final product distribution was provided by Fraunhofer, and this data comprised the preliminary test results as well as the predicted values for the processes still under development. The auxiliary material inputs were: surplus hydrogen for GtL plant (value provided by Fraunhofer); catalyst for GtL plant (estimated based on the literature review); and water and reagents for gas purification unit (estimated based on the literature review).

For the scrubbers, water consumption was calculated assuming 3:1 water to gas mass ratio [65]. Limestone required for sulfur removal was estimated based on data in Ref. [66]. Sulfuric acid amount that gives 5.6 pH of the acidic scrubber was assumed. Streams of removed contaminants - ammonia and calcium sulphate - were estimated based on the typical composition of agricultural residues, with the assumption that 95% of sulfur and 50% of nitrogen were transformed into H₂S and NH₃, respectively, during thermochemical conversion of biomass [67]. Hydrogen used in GtL partly comes from the electrooxidation step, but the remaining portion is assumed to come from non-renewable sources. Following Fraunhofer’s recommendation, hydrogen demand for the GtL conversion accounted for all carbon species in syngas (2:1 ratio for CO and 3:1 ratio for CO₂) and the stoichiometric H₂ amount was further increased 2.5 times. Thus calculated hydrogen demand exceeded the

Table 10
Typical mass balance of biorefinery (amounts in kg).

Flow	Amount	Database item	Source
Dry biomass to TCR	100.0		
TCR-water	25.0		F
TCR-oil	4.0		F
TCR-gas	35.0		F
Bio-coke	36.0	(P) RER: Petroleum coke at refinery	F
Heavy fraction of marine fuel	0.82	(P) RER: Heavy fuel oil at refinery (1.0wt.% S)	F
Medium fraction of marine fuel	1.80	(P) RER: Diesel mix at refinery	F
Light fraction of marine fuel	1.18	(P) RER: Kerosene / Jet A1 at refinery	F
Hydrogen from electrooxidation	0.7		F
Wastewater from electrooxidation	24.29	(P) Municipal waste water treatment (variable sludge treatment)	F
Acid for gas purification	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-5}$	(P) RER: Sulphuric acid (96%)	L
Base for gas purification	29.4	(P) RER: RER: Limestone, crushed stone fines (Grain size 0/2) (EN15804 A1-A3)	L
Water for gas purification	210	(P) RER: Water (desalinated; deionised)	L
External hydrogen to GtL	4.69	(P) RER: Hydrogen (Europipeline)	F
Cobalt (catalyst) to GtL	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-4}$	(P) GLO: Cobalt, refined (metal) CI	L
Silica (catalyst support) to GtL	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	(P) DE: Silica sand (Excavation and processing)	L
Wastewater from GtL	225.48	(P) Municipal waste water treatment (variable sludge treatment)	F + L
Bio-diesel	1.92	(P) RER: Diesel mix at filling station	F
Bio-gasoline	3.59	(P) RER: Gasoline mix (regular) at filling station	F
Propane	1.06	(P) RER: Propane at refinery	F
Paraffins	0.49	(P) RER: Wax / Paraffins at refinery	F

amount produced within the biorefinery. Wastewater stream was estimated based on the reaction stoichiometry. Residual water from the biorefining process is assumed to be treated in standard municipal wastewater treatment system. Tail gas from the GtL, based on Fraunhofer data, comprised N₂ and residual combustible compounds such as methane, propane, and butane. Following the business model approach, it was assumed that propane/butane present in the tail gas is recovered and becomes a product for sale. Excess H₂ would also be present in the tail gas – in the base case scenario it is not separated and recirculated. Product distribution of GtL unit was provided by Fraunhofer, according to Schulz-Flory equation. Lastly, the catalyst demand for the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis was estimated based on [67], where the requirement for cobalt catalyst with a 5-year lifetime (when continuously replenished) was reported. The composition of the catalyst was assumed following [68], as 12 wt% Co on SiO₂ support.

The environmental impacts of the modelled biomass processing will result mainly from the consumption of energy at the various stages of biorefining. Below is a list of the database items used for the sources of energy:

- (P) “RER: Thermal energy from natural gas” for the consumption of heat,
- (P) “RER: Electricity grid mix” for the consumption of electric energy.

Table 11 lists the assumptions on energy used during biomass processing. Additionally, Table 12 lists the streams of waste heat generated in the biorefinery, which could be potentially reused (but in the basic scenario are not).

A belt dryer with a heat requirement of 1300 kWh/t of evaporated water and electric energy consumption of 32 kWh/t of dry biomass was foreseen for biomass drying [69]. Following the information from project partners, the decrease of moisture content from 78 to 10 wt% was assumed, generating the evaporated water stream. In the base case scenario reusing this water was not considered. Electricity for grinding and pelletisation was estimated based on the specific energy demand for a conventional setup for woody biomass processing in a two-stage grinder and a mill pellet [70]. Electrical energy and heat demand for the TCR unit was provided by Fraunhofer, as it is in possession of an operating commercial scale reactor. Electrooxidation of pyrolysis water is a novel process currently under development in the scope of the project, thus the energy requirement for this unit was also based on Fraunhofer measurements. For the remaining processes, energy demand and generation were estimated with thermodynamic calculations supported by literature reports, to avoid scale-up errors that could arise while using values measured during the laboratory-scale experiments.

Table 11

Energy inputs to biomass processing (amounts in MJ per 100 kg of dried biomass at 10% moisture content).

Energy flow	Amount	Source
Heat for drying	1558.0	L
Electric energy for drying	11.4	L
Electric energy for grinding	49.39	L
Electric energy for pelletization	17.55	L
Heat for TCR	144.1	F
Electric energy for TCR	35.92	F
Heat for distillation	1.18	L
Electric energy for electrooxidation	396.3	F
Electric energy for gas purification	4.24	L
Electric energy for gas compression	158.37	L

Table 12

Waste heat streams in biorefinery (amounts in MJ per 100 kg of dried biomass at 10% moisture content).

Energy flow	Amount	Source
Heat generated during gas purification	32.86	L
Heat generated during gas compression	127.76	L
Heat generated in GtL	0.08	L
Heat generated in separation of GtL products	2.97	L
Heating value of tail gas from GtL	732.29	F

The heat duty of the distillation process was calculated assuming 47 MW heat required for 662.4 m³/h oil distillation, and with the assumption of the light crude oil density of 850 kg/m³ [71]. For the cooling of TCR-gas, it was assumed that it is cooled down from 700°C to 120°C. Recovered heat was calculated as the change in the physical enthalpy of the gas with the composition provided by Fraunhofer. Electrical energy requirement of the gas purification unit was assumed as 0.121 MJ/kg of syngas [67]. Compression of syngas combined with additional hydrogen was assumed as two-stage equal pressure rate compression (80% isentropic efficiency) with intercooling to 100°C [67]. To meet the requirements of the low-temperature Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, the outlet pressure and temperature were set to 25 bar and 250°C, respectively [67,72,73]. Power requirement and the heat generated during gas compression were calculated using Cantera thermodynamic properties library. Heat generated during the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis was estimated based on the standard enthalpy of reaction [74], and the heat recovered from the product separation column was calculated using specific heat capacity of gasoline, kerosene and paraffin [75], assuming cooling the products from 250°C to 20°C. The remaining tail gases from GtL (including methane and excess hydrogen) have a significant higher heating value of 40.6 MJ/kg. This energy could be recovered if the gases are combusted.

5.3. Combined process

For the inventory data for phytoremediation in the combined process, all data from Tables 5 and 8 have been recalculated per 1 ha and then average values (from all four pilot sites) have been calculated. Similarly, an average biomass yield has been calculated (from values presented in Table 7). On the basis of average biomass yield, the LCI values have then been upscaled under an assumption that 3900 Mg of dry biomass is produced.

Inventory data for biomass processing in the combined process is exactly the same as presented in section 5.2.

6. Results and their interpretation

Environmental impacts of the combined process of phytoremediation and biomass processing calculated with regard to its functional unit (“processing 3900 Mg of dry biomass”) are presented in Table 13. Selected, most interesting results of LCIA of the subprocesses (calculated with regard to their own functional units) are presented in Tables 14–18 for phytoremediation and in Tables 19–23 for biomass processing. The selected categories, especially *Climate Change* and *Human Toxicity* showcase the most important results from the perspective of the scope of Phy2Climate project. In addition, they are the most representative regarding the contributions of particular activity groups to the total environmental scores. Other impact categories, not shown in detail, display similar contributions of particular activity groups to the total scores.

Since the environmental impacts can have both positive and negative values, the percentages have been calculated by dividing the value of environmental impact in the given group by the sum of absolute values of environmental impacts of all groups of activities. The percentage contributions therefore do not sum up to 100 %, but their absolute

Table 13
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of phytoremediation combined with biomass processing.

Impact category	Phyto-remediation	Biomass processing	Total	Unit
Climate Change - total	5.28E+06	3.97E+05	5.28E+06	kg CO ₂ eq.
<i>Climate Change, biogenic</i>	1.41E+04	2.53E+04	1.41E+04	kg CO ₂ eq.
<i>Climate Change, fossil</i>	5.22E+06	3.76E+05	5.22E+06	kg CO ₂ eq.
<i>Climate Change, land use and land use change</i>	4.47E+04	-4.13E+03	4.47E+04	kg CO ₂ eq.
Ozone depletion	2.35E-06	4.37E-05	2.35E-06	kg CFC-11 eq.
Ecotoxicity, freshwater - total	-5.80E+07	-1.35E+07	-5.80E+07	CTUe
<i>Ecotoxicity, freshwater inorganics</i>	-5.22E+07	-1.33E+07	-5.22E+07	CTUe
<i>Ecotoxicity, freshwater organics</i>	-5.82E+06	-1.96E+05	-5.82E+06	CTUe
Acidification	5.71E+04	6.22E+03	5.71E+04	mole of H ⁺ eq.
<i>Eutrophication, freshwater</i>	1.99E+01	1.07E+01	1.99E+01	kg P eq.
<i>Eutrophication, marine</i>	2.88E+04	2.24E+03	2.88E+04	kg N eq.
<i>Eutrophication, terrestrial</i>	3.17E+05	2.36E+04	3.17E+05	mole of N eq.
Human toxicity, cancer - total	-5.55E-02	8.46E-04	-5.55E-02	CTUh
<i>Human toxicity, cancer inorganics</i>	-4.78E-02	-1.50E-04	-4.78E-02	CTUh
<i>Human toxicity, cancer organics</i>	-7.71E-03	9.96E-04	-7.71E-03	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer - total	-8.93E+00	2.12E-02	-8.93E+00	CTUh
<i>Human toxicity, non-cancer inorganics</i>	-8.92E+00	2.07E-02	-8.92E+00	CTUh
<i>Human toxicity, non-cancer organics</i>	-1.08E-02	4.21E-04	-1.08E-02	CTUh
Particulate matter	1.14E+00	5.71E-02	1.14E+00	Disease incidences
Ionising radiation, human health	5.35E+04	1.31E+06	5.35E+04	kBq U ²³⁵ eq.
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	8.06E+04	5.76E+03	8.06E+04	kg NMVOC eq.
Land use	-6.02E+10	1.52E+07	-6.02E+10	Pt
Resource use, fossils	7.12E+07	9.07E+07	7.12E+07	MJ
Resource use, minerals and metals	3.87E-01	3.54E-01	3.87E-01	kg Sb eq.
Water use	2.60E+07	5.70E+05	2.60E+07	m ³ world equiv.

values do. Positive values of the environmental impact indicators mean an adverse impact (burden) on the environment, while negative values mean that adverse impacts are avoided.

The obtained results of the LCIA for phytoremediation show that consumption of fuel is the greatest contributor to almost all impact categories. Only the use of fertilizers has a comparable impact in some categories (for example *Ozone depletion*). Removal of contaminants from the soil has a beneficial impact on categories *Ecotoxicity* and *Human toxicity*. These beneficial impacts generally outweigh the adverse impacts caused by other groups of activities, resulting in an overall negative value of these environmental impact indicators.

It must be stressed that the presented results are based on inventory data from the first year of phytoremediation. It is expected that in the subsequent years, the rate of contaminants removal will decrease, which will reduce the positive impacts in *Ecotoxicity* and *Human toxicity* categories. However, at the same time, the biomass yield may increase, potentially improving the environmental impacts of the entire process.

Inventory data on the removal of contaminants from the soil is a valuable piece of information, because if it is included in LCI as “negative emissions”, it directly affects the LCIA results in *Ecotoxicity* and *Human toxicity* categories, reflecting the very purpose of soil remediation activities. However, it is inherently burdened by high uncertainties, especially in the case of hydrocarbon removal calculated using formula (2) due to a very heterogeneous spatial distribution of contaminants in the soil. An additional problem and source of uncertainty is the variation of phytoremediation performance (contaminant removal rate) in the subsequent years. It could be solved by averaging the soil contaminant removal rate over 20 years (or whatever the actual phytoremediation period would be). However, at the current stage of the Phy2Climate project there is not enough data to formulate and extrapolate trends of phytoremediation performance over time.

Although results from several pilot sites are reported, they should not be interpreted as comparison between these sites. This is not intended; such comparison would be unjustified due to the differences in level and type of pollution, as well as differences in climate zones.

Use of inventory data on agricultural activities gathered at small scale pilot sites (as presented in this study) is impractical, because the reported consumption of fuel, water and fertilizers is strongly site-specific and not representative of larger scale agricultural activities. For scaled up phytoremediation sites, the specific fuel and resources consumption for agricultural activities is expected to be lower. Therefore, for the analyses in the next phase of the project, generalized agricultural datasets should be used, as long as a decrease of biomass yield compared to uncontaminated land is accounted for.

For the biomass processing, three groups of activities negatively stand out in the LCIA: Drying and pelletizing, Gas to Liquid and Electrooxidation. This is a result of high consumption of heat and electric energy in these activities, and in the case of GTL also the use of external hydrogen. Even though the avoided use of fossil fuels, especially coke, results in reductions of greenhouse gas emissions, they are outweighed by the emissions associated with energy consumption in the biorefinery and, as a result, the overall impact of the biorefinery in the field of *Climate change* is adverse. In fact, the only categories in which the biorefinery gets a positive environmental score, are *Ecotoxicity, freshwater* and *Human toxicity, cancer inorganics*.

LCIA of averaged phytoremediation combined with biomass processing shows positive impact of the proposed technology on the *Ecotoxicity* and *Human toxicity* impact categories, as well as *Land use*. However, the environmental impacts in all other categories are adverse. This is a direct consequence of negative energy balance of the system and assumed utilization of market average (not fully renewable) energy sources for driving the biorefinery (quantified in the *Resource use, fossils* impact category). Hence, these results should be interpreted with caution as they present the pessimistic case with high input of external energy required. In practice, the specific fuel consumption for agricultural activities can be lowered by scaling up the phytoremediation sites, and the specific energy consumption of biorefinery can be lowered by optimizing its configuration.

This first overview of the biorefinery concept points towards a few potentially crucial aspects in the operation of the system:

- The magnitude of environmental impacts of biorefinery is mainly determined by the source of energy used for driving the processes. In the current analysis, the most widely available, average (not fully renewable) sources of energy have been assumed. Changing the energy sources to renewable ones could greatly improve the environmental impacts of biorefinery. However, this would depend on

Table 14
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of phytoremediation: Climate change, fossil.

<i>Climate Change, fossil</i>	ARG		SRB		LTU		ESP	
	kg CO2 eq.	% of total						
Irrigation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Use of fertilizers	8.97E+01	0.87%	4.67E+01	18.36%	3.79E+02	5.05%	4.33E+00	0.68%
Use of pesticides	0.00E+00	0.00%	1.54E+00	0.61%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Land transformation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Fuel & energy consumption	1.03E+04	99.13%	2.06E+02	81.03%	7.14E+03	94.95%	6.37E+02	99.32%
Total	1.04E+04		2.54E+02		7.52E+03		6.41E+02	

Table 15
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of phytoremediation: Human toxicity, non-cancer - total.

<i>Human toxicity, non-cancer - total</i>	ARG		SRB		LTU		ESP	
	CTUh	% of total	CTUh	% of total	CTUh	% of total	CTUh	% of total
Irrigation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Use of fertilizers	7.71E-07	0.01%	4.15E-07	0.13%	1.86E-06	2.12%	2.11E-08	0.30%
Use of pesticides	0.00E+00	0.00%	2.73E-06	0.87%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Land transformation	-1.43E-02	-99.38%	-3.09E-04	-98.42%	-2.43E-05	-27.58%	-1.41E-06	-20.09%
Fuel & energy consumption	8.90E-05	0.62%	1.81E-06	0.58%	6.19E-05	70.31%	5.59E-06	79.61%
Total	-1.42E-02		-3.04E-04		3.95E-05		4.20E-06	

Table 16
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of phytoremediation: Ecotoxicity, freshwater - total.

<i>Ecotoxicity, freshwater - total</i>	ARG		SRB		LTU		ESP	
	CTUe	% of total	CTUe	% of total	CTUe	% of total	CTUe	% of total
Irrigation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Use of fertilizers	2.18E+02	0.08%	4.53E+02	3.58%	1.01E+03	1.34%	1.10E+01	0.13%
Use of pesticides	0.00E+00	0.00%	6.75E+02	5.33%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Land transformation	-1.77E+05	-64.09%	-9.54E+03	-75.36%	-6.19E+03	-8.21%	-2.05E+03	-25.01%
Fuel & energy consumption	9.90E+04	35.83%	1.99E+03	15.73%	6.82E+04	90.44%	6.15E+03	74.86%
Total	-7.78E+04		-6.42E+03		6.30E+04		4.11E+03	

Table 17
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of phytoremediation: Eutrophication, terrestrial.

<i>Eutrophication, terrestrial</i>	ARG		SRB		LTU		ESP	
	mole of N eq.	% of total	mole of N eq.	% of total	mole of N eq.	% of total	mole of N eq.	% of total
Irrigation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Use of fertilizers	7.51E-01	0.12%	1.53E-01	1.13%	1.93E+00	0.43%	2.24E-02	0.05%
Use of pesticides	0.00E+00	0.00%	8.07E-03	0.06%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Land transformation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Fuel & energy consumption	6.32E+02	99.88%	1.33E+01	98.81%	4.50E+02	99.57%	4.12E+01	99.95%
Total	6.33E+02		1.35E+01		4.52E+02		4.12E+01	

the type of existing energy sources at the location of the biorefinery, because installing additional renewable energy sources (for example photovoltaics) is out of the scope of the Phy2Climate project.

- It was assumed that biomass is actively dried using heat of (by default) non-renewable origin. In practice, the harvested biomass can be just left at the field to dry using solar energy. It would greatly

improve the environmental impacts, because currently "Drying and pelletizing" is the greatest contributor to the *Resource use, fossil* category. This variant will be analyzed in further iterations of LCA.

- The possibilities of heat recirculation in the biorefinery, which would reduce the use of external energy sources, will be highly dependent

Table 18
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of phytoremediation: Ozone depletion.

Ozone depletion	ARG		SRB		LTU		ESP	
	kg CFC-11 eq.	% of total						
Irrigation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Use of fertilizers	5.80E-10	30.08%	9.05E-11	71.78%	1.81E-09	28.89%	2.13E-11	20.61%
Use of pesticides	0.00E+00	0.00%	9.04E-12	7.18%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Land transformation	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%	0.00E+00	0.00%
Fuel & energy consumption	1.35E-09	69.92%	2.65E-11	21.05%	4.47E-09	71.11%	8.20E-11	79.39%
Total	1.93E-09		1.26E-10		6.28E-09		1.03E-10	

Table 19
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of biomass processing: Climate change, fossil.

Climate Change, fossil	kg CO ₂ eq.	% of total
Drying and pelletizing	4.35E+06	29.50%
Transport of biomass	2.85E+04	0.19%
Biorefinery: TCR	5.03E+05	3.41%
Biorefinery: GTL	1.29E+06	8.73%
Biorefinery: oil distillation	3.10E+03	0.02%
Biorefinery: electrooxidation	1.39E+06	9.41%
Utilization of waste products	4.26E+03	0.03%
Avoided use of liquid fuels	-1.31E+06	-8.89%
Avoided use of coke	-5.71E+06	-38.68%
Avoided use of other products	-1.67E+05	-1.13%
Total	3.83E+05	

Table 20
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of biomass processing: Human toxicity, non-cancer – total.

Human toxicity, non-cancer - total	CTUh	% of total
Drying and pelletizing	2.22E-02	28.19%
Transport of biomass	2.43E-04	0.31%
Biorefinery: TCR	2.54E-03	3.23%
Biorefinery: GTL	1.53E-02	19.50%
Biorefinery: oil distillation	1.58E-05	0.02%
Biorefinery: electrooxidation	6.86E-03	8.72%
Utilization of waste products	2.76E-03	3.51%
Avoided use of liquid fuels	-9.28E-03	-11.80%
Avoided use of coke	-1.81E-02	-23.04%
Avoided use of other products	-1.32E-03	-1.68%
Total	2.12E-02	

Table 21
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of biomass processing: Ecotoxicity, freshwater - total.

Ecotoxicity, freshwater - total	CTUe	% of total
Drying and pelletizing	2.23E+06	2.89%
Transport of biomass	2.73E+05	0.35%
Biorefinery: TCR	7.91E+05	1.03%
Biorefinery: GTL	2.01E+07	26.15%
Biorefinery: oil distillation	4.74E+02	0.00%
Biorefinery: electrooxidation	8.12E+06	10.55%
Utilization of waste products	2.20E+05	0.29%
Avoided use of liquid fuels	-1.23E+07	-15.96%
Avoided use of coke	-3.07E+07	-39.88%
Avoided use of other products	-2.23E+06	-2.90%
Total	-1.35E+07	

Table 22
Life Cycle Impact Assessment of biomass processing: Eutrophication, terrestrial.

Eutrophication, terrestrial	mole of N eq.	% of total
Drying and pelletizing	1.32E+04	36.10%
Transport of biomass	8.53E+01	0.23%
Biorefinery: TCR	1.75E+03	4.80%
Biorefinery: GTL	7.59E+03	20.82%
Biorefinery: oil distillation	8.89E+00	0.02%
Biorefinery: electrooxidation	7.42E+03	20.34%
Utilization of waste products	3.30E+01	0.09%
Avoided use of liquid fuels	-2.21E+03	-6.06%
Avoided use of coke	-3.92E+03	-10.74%
Avoided use of other products	-2.90E+02	-0.80%
Total	2.36E+04	

on the biorefinery setup. Each scenario might result in a quite different heat demand/generation outcome.

- Conversion of the total stream of syngas requires large amount of excess hydrogen. Fossil-fuel based hydrogen will impair the environmental footprint of the system, while production of hydrogen by electrolysis will require high energy input.
- The unreacted hydrogen from the GtL could be recirculated, thus needing additional equipment and energy, yet reducing the stream of required external hydrogen. Otherwise it will end up in the tail gas,

resulting in its high calorific value. Combustion of this gas could provide heat needed in other biorefinery processes.

- The fate of CO₂ in the syngas will affect the technical aspects of the biorefinery concept, thus influencing the outcomes of economic and environmental analyses. Sequestration of CO₂ will generate additional waste streams and will increase energy consumption; utilization of CO₂ in GtL requires additional H₂ and might require additional conversion step such as reversed water gas shift reaction; recirculation of CO₂ (e.g. to the TCR reactor) might affect the product distribution.

Table 23

Life Cycle Impact Assessment of biomass processing: Ozone depletion.

Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq.	% of total
Drying and pelletizing	5.22E-06	11.66%
Transport of biomass	2.49E-09	0.01%
Biorefinery: TCR	2.33E-06	5.21%
Biorefinery: GTL	1.10E-05	24.65%
Biorefinery: oil distillation	1.29E-10	0.00%
Biorefinery: electrooxidation	2.56E-05	57.24%
Utilization of waste products	2.90E-08	0.06%
Avoided use of liquid fuels	-1.54E-07	-0.34%
Avoided use of coke	-3.35E-07	-0.75%
Avoided use of other products	-3.38E-08	-0.08%
Total	4.37E-05	

- TCR process carried out under inert atmosphere requires providing N₂, and furthermore, N₂ is present in the syngas and needs to be separated, or otherwise, it will increase energy consumption of the compressor and also possibly affect the operation of the GTL unit.

Results of the biorefinery inventory suggest that the abovementioned aspects should be considered while developing future scenarios. It seems that the main focus should be paid to the syngas processing – percent of the syngas directed to the GTL unit, the arrangement of N₂, H₂ and CO₂ streams, and the parameters of the GTL process itself.

The presented results should not be viewed as representative of the final application of Phy2Climate technology. Optimization works will be carried out in the next steps of the project. Selected scenarios identified as the most promising can be then evaluated using LCA approach proposed hereby, and a sensitivity analysis should allow estimating conditions that will ensure positive environmental impact of the phytoremediation-biorefinery system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomasz Simla: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Agnieszka Korus:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Karolina Petela:** Validation, Project administration. **Wojciech Stanek:** Supervision. **Markus Ortner:** Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Andrzej Szłęk:** Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

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